

Perceptions of India: A Journey Through Historical and Cultural Lenses in Sam Miller's *A Strange Kind of Paradise*

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Abstract

Sam Miller is a highly renowned writer and journalist. Despite being born and raised in London, he has resided in India for the past 25 years. Therefore, establishing an emotional bond and sense of affiliation with India. Since the early 90s, he has been affiliated with the BBC as a television and radio correspondent in New Delhi. In addition, he served as a correspondent for the BBC in Afghanistan, Pakistan, Bangladesh, the Balkans, and Northern Ireland.

*Published in 2009 by Penguin India, his first book 'Delhi: Adventures in a Megacity' earned him a reputation and popularity among renowned writers. Subsequently, he has authored other literary works, such as *A Strange Kind Of Paradise: India Through Foreign Eyes* (2014), and *Fathers* (2017), and has also undertaken the translation of *The Marvellous (but Authentic) Adventures of Captain Corcoran by Alfred Assollant* (2017). Additionally, he has authored *Blue Guide India*, a comprehensive guidebook that provides an intricate account of India's art, architecture, and history for tourists. His works depict India as a fusion of historical and contemporary elements, combining Eastern and Western influences, as well as modern and traditional aspects. Miller's writings expose the diverse perspectives, various concepts, and biases that foreign tourists hold about India. He also endeavours to dispel any confusion or misunderstandings that readers may have by sharing his own comprehensive understanding and personal experiences of India.*

Keywords: Indian History, journalist, emotional bond, historical and contemporary elements, modern and traditional aspects, etc.

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Introduction

India is renowned for its harmonious coexistence of diverse cultures, its opulent historical legacy, its rich heritage, and its steadfast adherence to tradition. Indian culture, being one of the most ancient civilisations, is widely considered to be the preeminent culture by numerous authorities. It is not an exaggeration to state that Indian civilisation is one of the few civilisations that have endured to this day, despite several invasions, and attacks on its territory, people, and culture. Her captivating beauty and enchanting stories have consistently captivated and resonated with people worldwide throughout history.

For centuries, travellers from all corners of the globe have been to this place, returning with diverse narratives and anecdotes to share with the rest of the world. The individuals who migrated to India, including Greeks, Mughals, Chinese, Arabs, and others, each contributed to the projection of India in their distinct manner. This article aims to examine the experiences of foreign travellers who visited India and resided there for an extended period. It will focus on how these individuals formed their perceptions of India based on the selected work of Sam Miller, titled *A Strange Kind of Paradise: India Through Foreign Eyes*. This study examines the perspectives of Greek, Muslim, and Chinese explorers and their portrayal of India in their works.

India has long been a land of intrigue and fascination for both its inhabitants and outsiders, a place where history and culture intertwine to create a tapestry rich in diversity and complexity. The perceptions of India, shaped by centuries of narratives, are as varied as its people, reflecting a land that is at once ancient and modern, mystical and pragmatic. These perceptions are often filtered through historical and cultural lenses that reveal the complexities of its civilization, from the grandeur of its empires to the everyday lives of its people. In Sam Miller's *A Strange Kind of Paradise: India Through Foreign Eyes*, the author embarks on a journey to explore these multifaceted views of India, delving into the country's history and culture to offer a nuanced perspective. Through his exploration, Miller highlights how India has been perceived by both its own citizens and foreign observers, shedding light on the ways in which these perceptions have evolved over time and continue to shape the understanding of this vast and diverse nation.

A Strange Kind of Paradise: India Through Foreign Eyes by Sam Miller (2014) is a book that explores the history and culture of India as seen through the eyes of foreign travelers, writers, and conquerors over the centuries. The book delves into how outsiders have perceived and represented India, from ancient times to the present, examining the myths, misconceptions, and fascinations that have shaped the world's understanding of the country.

Miller weaves together historical accounts, travel narratives, and his own experiences as a long-time resident of India to provide a nuanced and layered portrait of the nation. He reflects on how India's diverse and complex identity has been influenced by external views and how these views have, in turn, shaped the nation's self-perception. The book is both a travelogue and a historical exploration, offering insights into India's cultural intersections, contradictions, and the enduring allure it holds for those from abroad.

Miller embarks on an exploration of India's historical and contemporary aspects by retracing the footsteps of the Greek explorers, who are believed to be the earliest visitors to the country.

Scylax of Caryanda was a Greek explorer, geographer, and navigator who lived during the late 6th and early 5th centuries BCE. He is best known for his exploration under the commission of Persian King Darius the Great. Scylax was tasked with exploring the course of the Indus River and its eventual flow into the Indian Ocean, which was of significant interest to the Persian Empire as they sought to expand their influence into the Indian subcontinent.

The expedition that Scylax undertook was one of the earliest recorded European voyages to India. His journey started from the city of Caspatyrus (modern-day Peshawar in Pakistan) in the region of Gandhara and involved navigating the Indus River down to the sea. This journey provided crucial geographical knowledge about the region and helped Darius to understand and later conquer parts of the Indus Valley.

Scylax is credited with writing a periplus, a type of navigational guide, based on his travels. This work, known as the *Periplus of Scylax*, was a maritime itinerary describing the coastal regions and the peoples he encountered along the way. Though the original work has not survived, later historians and geographers, such as Herodotus and Strabo, referenced it, indicating its importance in the ancient world.

Scylax's accounts, which often blended factual observations with fantastical elements, were typical of ancient explorers who encountered cultures vastly different from their own. His descriptions of mythical creatures, like the Skiapodes and Monophthalmoi, reflect the Greek tendency to interpret foreign lands as places of wonder and strangeness. While modern historians view these accounts with skepticism, they provide insight into how ancient Greeks perceived and imagined distant lands like India. In addition to his explorations in India, Scylax was known for his broader contributions to Greek geography. His work influenced later geographical thought and exploration in the classical world, serving as a reference for understanding the far reaches of the Persian Empire and the wider world beyond Greece.

Scylax, the renowned mariner and navigator of his era, served under the Persian King Darius the Great. He is often regarded as the earliest explorer to have journeyed to India. Scylax's written accounts describe encounters with unfamiliar individuals and groups. India, as he experienced it, was a land teeming with peculiar narratives and extraordinary phenomena. He recounts his encounters with Skiapodes, sometimes known as shadow feet people. These individuals possessed feet of such significant size that they were able to find protection from the intense heat of the sun by reclining and elevating their feet in the air. (13)

Additionally, there are records of individuals with a single eye, known as the Monophthalmoi. According to Scylax, these individuals possessed a singular eye positioned in the centre of their forehead. Additionally, he reportedly encountered the Enotikoittoi, a group known for their exceptionally huge ears that were capable of being wrapped around their body and used as sleeping bags. The veracity of these accounts regarding Scylax remains unknown.

However, Scylax's writings portrayed India as a region teeming with peculiar and extraordinary creatures. He had vivid fantasies about India and its people.

The tales of Scylax were comparable to Star Trek in their time, as they were a widely enjoyed combination of science and fantasy," (Miller Pg. 13)

Another notable explorer is the renowned Herodotus, often referred to as the progenitor of historical studies. The earliest reference to India can be traced back to his literary composition *Histories*, which was penned in 440 BCE. He presents accounts of colossal ants

discovered in India that excavate for gold, as well as instances of Indian males ejaculating black semen.

Ctesias of Cnidus was a Greek physician and historian who lived in the 5th century BCE and served as a court physician to the Persian King Artaxerxes II. He is known for his work *Indica*, a compilation of accounts about India based on the stories he heard from Persian sources and travelers at the royal court. Although Ctesias never visited India himself, his writings provided a fascinating, though often fantastical, view of the subcontinent, much like other ancient Greek accounts.

In *Indica*, Ctesias described various animals, plants, and people of India, often blending fact with fiction. One of the more peculiar creatures he mentioned was a tiny bird with supposedly deadly excrement. According to Ctesias, this bird, which he described as very small, had the dangerous habit of hiding its waste. If a person were to consume even a tiny amount of this excrement, as small as a sesame seed, it would cause death before the end of the day. (13)

Ctesias' accounts, like those of other ancient writers, should be approached with caution, as they often contain a mix of observation, hearsay, and myth. His descriptions are frequently exaggerated or entirely mythical, contributing to the exotic and mysterious image of India that prevailed in the classical world. These stories, while not scientifically credible, played a significant role in shaping the Greek and later Roman perceptions of India as a land of wonders and dangers. In addition to his descriptions of avian creatures, Ctesias also wrote about other fantastical elements of Indian flora and fauna, including monstrous animals, plants with extraordinary properties, and mythical peoples with strange physical features. His work contributed to the rich tapestry of Greco-Roman imagination about the East, influencing subsequent writers and travelers who further embellished these tales. Despite the dubious accuracy of his accounts, Ctesias' *Indica* remains an important source for understanding how ancient Greeks viewed the distant and mysterious land of India.

Both Herodotus and Ctesias depicted India as possessing abundant natural resources. They aptly defined India as a densely populated and diverse nation. Therefore, not only did they invent everything in their stories, but they also accurately depicted certain aspects that are

observable in the present. India is a densely populated and diverse country. It is undeniably a significant repository of abundant natural resources in the present day as well.

Some people argue that the other elaborate narratives recounted by Herodotus and Ctesias may have undergone alterations during the process of translation. Sam Miller gives a counterargument to dispel the confusion surrounding these stories. According to him, the large ants were marmots that transported gold nuggets to the surface through their burrowing. Alternatively, the text suggests that the story serves as a metaphor for India being a prosperous land, a theme that continues to be a prominent aspect of India's portrayal in literature up to the present day. (14)

Alexander of Macedon, was a Greek individual who had the ambition not only to explore India but also to establish dominion over it by conquest. However, he was unable to accomplish both tasks simultaneously. Following his demise, General Seleucus dispatched an ambassador named Megasthenes to India to conduct an exploration of the region. Megasthenes explored the empire of Chandragupta Maurya, who was the reigning monarch and held significant influence during that era. He travelled to the Mauryan capital, Pataliputra, which is now known as Patna in the state of Bihar.

Indica, his work, is widely regarded as the most authoritative reference on India. He depicted Patna during the Mauryan era as an exceedingly crowded city in his writings. He was astounded by the abundant natural resources and wealth that India possessed. He wrote extensively on India's bountiful terrain, the tigers, the hospitality and reverence towards strangers, the architectural wonders, the skilled engineers, the talented musicians, and the majestic elephants. They all left him in a state of wonder.

The *Indica* by Megasthenes is the inaugural and noteworthy written record of India authored by a non-native. He provides a comprehensive account of the political and social structure of the city of Pataliputra, which consists of six committees, each comprising five members. These committees are responsible for overseeing various aspects such as industry, arts, foreign affairs, birth and death records, trade and commerce, manufacturing, and tax collecting. (21) Officials were responsible for overseeing waterways, constructing roads, and inspecting sluices. Unlike Ctesias, who never visited India, Megasthenes actually traveled and

lived there, providing a more direct and, to some extent, more accurate account of Indian society, geography, and culture during his time.

The *Indica* by Megasthenes is a descriptive account of India, its people, customs, geography, flora, fauna, and political systems. It includes descriptions of the cities, rivers, and the administration under Chandragupta Maurya. He also wrote about the caste system, the practices of different groups in Indian society, and the philosophical traditions, including the lives of the Brahmins and the Sramanas (ascetics).

Despite its importance, Megasthenes' *Indica* survives only in fragments cited by later authors such as Strabo, Arrian, and Diodorus Siculus. These fragments have been instrumental in reconstructing ancient Indian history and understanding the perceptions of India in the ancient Greek world. However, like many ancient accounts, even Megasthenes' *Indica* contains some inaccuracies and exaggerations, but it is generally considered a more reliable source than earlier works like that of Ctesias. Both Ctesias and Megasthenes wrote works titled *Indica*, but Megasthenes' account is more highly regarded for its relatively accurate depiction of India based on first-hand experience.

Chandragupta possessed the most extensive military force in India, and possibly even in the world. He commanded an army consisting of 60,000 infantry soldiers, 30,000 cavalry warriors, and 8,000 elephants. There was no presence of slavery in the Mauryan empire.

Megasthenes regarded India as a land of wealth, bustling cities, efficient governance, remarkable progress, and impressive infrastructure. He witnessed remarkable achievements not in the shape of peculiar beings, but rather in the exceptional accomplishments of individuals in various domains.

In addition to the Greeks, a significant number of Chinese Monks travelled to India during the rapid development of Buddhism throughout Asia. India held great religious significance for China and the Chinese people due to its association with Buddha, who resided there and attained enlightenment. A Chinese traveller who visited India was Tripitaka, also known as Xuanzang. He differed from other spiritual explorers who, in their pursuit of the divine, disregard the world surrounding them. Tripitaka exhibited distinct characteristics. His literature provides a comprehensive and early depiction of Kashmir and Varanasi. Tripitaka

depicted various regions of India throughout his travels. He characterised the individuals residing in the Kullu Valley as having a rough and ordinary physical appearance and being greatly affected by goitre and tumours. They possess a character that is tough and aggressive; they value principles of fairness and courage. (66)

In addition, he journeyed to the city of Prayag, also known as Allahabad, now called Prayagraj, where he discussed the pleasant weather and amiable demeanour of the locals. The inhabitants of that place had a strong passion for acquiring knowledge and were highly receptive to unorthodox ideas. He also made clichéd remarks about the Kashmiri people, stating that they possess physical beauty and charm but are inherently deceitful. His passion for India and its people peaked when he discussed Bihar and Nalanda.

His jaw dropped when he first saw Nalanda. He provided a detailed account of the seminary, which was the highlight of his journey. The author described a large wall that encircled a seminary accommodating ten thousand monks. Inside, there were multi-storey chambers for the monks, featuring dragon projections and colourful eaves. The pillars were carved and decorated with red pearls, and the balustrades were richly adorned. The roofs were covered with tiles that reflected light in a myriad of colours. (69)

The chronicles of Tripitaka reveal that India was not solely characterised by the peculiar and marvellous tales recounted by the Greeks, but it was also regarded as a sacred destination where individuals may seek spiritual enlightenment. It served as a hub for acquiring information and wisdom. The location was inhabited by individuals from diverse and distinct cultural backgrounds. The location was associated with Buddha. Furthermore, this location suffered the loss of its valuable repository of wisdom and information due to the influence of Muslims and Mughals. A Muslim warrior set fire to the seminary at Nalanda due to its lack of any copies of the Koran. Millions of books were destroyed and incinerated, destroying India's most valuable and advanced centre of knowledge. The store of truth was plundered thrice by the Muslim conquerors.

The Mughal Travellers

Miller commences his analysis of the Muslim perspective and disposition towards India by focussing on Mahmud of Ghazni. He is widely regarded as one of the most despised Muslim

monarchs in Indian history. India was a significant reservoir of riches for him. On each occasion that he invaded India, he would transport substantial amounts of gold, silver, and gems back with him.

All of these items were confiscated from Hindu temples. They demolished Hindu temples and plundered them. The Somnath temple was among the structures that were demolished by his army in 1026. According to his historians, Mahmud did not hesitate to kill innocent Hindus and plunder their temples. According to the author, India was merely regarded as a means of acquiring wealth by him, (82)

According to Mahmud's historians and his invasions, India possessed a significant quantity of gold, silver, and other valuable gemstones. The army of Mahmud violently confiscated a significant quantity of elephants.

Alberuni, a renowned figure in Mahmud's Court, was not originally from Ghazni but was forcibly relocated there from Uzbekistan. Following Mahmud's demise, Alberuni emerged as a prominent critic, providing an accurate depiction of India in the aftermath of Mahmud's conquest. According to him, Mahmud destroyed the economic success of the country, causing the people of India to be dispersed like tiny particles of dust in every direction. (83) Similar to other European orientalist of the period, Alberuni saw India, particularly Hindu religion and culture, as being of lesser value compared to his faith and civilisation. He stated that the Vedas, Upanishads, and other scriptures are merely verbose. The mathematical and astronomical procedures and equations are a combination of valuable and worthless elements. In addition, he expressed his disapproval of Indian culture, asserting that their categorisation of spiritual entities is disorganised and arbitrary, and their method of measuring little units of time is excessively meticulous and silly (Miller p. 84). He characterises the Hindu faith as replete with 'repulsive fabrications' and 'foolish beliefs'.

Alberuni meticulously documented various aspects of India, including its social order, scientific and mathematical advancements, culinary traditions, and caste system. While he had an appreciation for Indian intellectuals and acquired knowledge of Indian philosophy and Sanskrit, he also expressed criticism towards the Vedic culture of India. Ibn Battuta, another Muslim traveller, visited India. He was a Moroccan explorer of the 14th century. His accounts offer an intricate portrayal of Tughalq's Court. According to Ibn Battuta, who was briefed by

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another traveller when he approached India, the Sultan of Delhi, Muhammad ibn Tughlaq, displayed remarkable hospitality towards strangers entering his territory. He had a strong affinity for receiving gifts and displayed great generosity while giving return gifts.

During his visit to the Sultan, Ibn Battuta presented the Sultan with white slaves, horses, and camels as gifts. As a reciprocation, the Sultan dispatched to him several silver Dinars and substantial amounts of grain, meat, sugar, and nuts. Ibn Battuta had a sense of gratitude towards the Sultan.

While journeying over the nation, he also came across numerous peculiar individuals. His writings also have a resemblance to the works of early Greek explorers. According to him, he claimed to have witnessed yogis who can levitate along with their sandals, individuals with dog-like jaws, humans transforming into tigers and extracting a man's heart without causing any visible injury, and in present-day Sri Lanka, monkeys engaging in sexual activity with women. (91)

Throughout history, individuals from various walks of life have been visiting India for diverse reasons and objectives. These include diplomats, pilgrims, missionaries, artists, soul searchers, refugees, wanderers, and lovers, among others. Each individual possesses a unique perspective, understanding, and viewpoint, as well as preconceived notions and biases, which are frequently inaccurate, false, and nonsensical, regarding this vast nation.

In his prologue, Miller elucidates that India has consistently eluded simple categorisation, leaving visitors perplexed as to whether it is a realm of immense affluence or abject destitution, of spiritual renunciation or unapologetic materialism, of fasting or excessive indulgence, of refined eroticism or sexual prudishness, of corruption or moral ascendancy. They likely refuse to acknowledge that it might encompass all of these factors, as well as everything in the middle.

To conclude, in *A Strange Kind of Paradise: India Through Foreign Eyes*, Sam Miller masterfully weaves together historical narratives, cultural reflections, and personal insights to offer a multifaceted portrayal of India. By examining the perceptions and experiences of foreign travelers and observers, Miller highlights the complex interplay between myth and reality in shaping India's image in the global consciousness. The book not only challenges

conventional stereotypes but also deepens our understanding of how external perspectives have influenced both the historical narrative and contemporary identity of India. Ultimately, Miller's work serves as a reminder of the richness and diversity of India's cultural heritage and the ongoing dialogue between the East and the West.

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